

Chemical Investigation of *Sonchus oleraceus* Linn

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Sonchus oleraceus Linn., a member of the family Compositae is found throughout India. In Patna it is locally known as "Titaliya". A gum formed by the evaporation of the juice of the plant is stated to be a powerful hydragogue cathartic and an infusion of its roots and leaves is said to be used as a tonic and febrifuge¹.

A review of the literature showed that no work has been done on this plant and therefore the chemical investigation of this plant was undertaken.

Well dried whole plant obtained from Patna (Bihar) on extraction with light petroleum ether in a soxhlet apparatus gave a greenish white gummy mass, which on repeated crystallisations from petroleum ether gave colourless fine needles m.p. 180–85°.

The product m.p. 180–85° on thin layer chromatography was found to be a mixture and therefore it was purified by preparative thin layer chromatography on silica gel utilising benzene : petroleum ether (40–60° fraction) 50 : 50 and gave colourless crystals m.p. 223–24°. It showed only one spot on T.L.C. (cf. taraxasterol m.p. 225–26°).

The crude product m.p. 180–85° was acetylated in the usual manner in the cold and purified by preparative T.L.C. It gave colourless crystals m.p. 253–54° (cf. taraxasterol acetate m.p. 256–57°). On benzylation, the original product gave a benzoate m.p. 259–60° (cf. taraxasterol benzoate m.p. 260–62°).

The original compound on hydrogenation with platinum oxide and hydrogen at ordinary temperature and pressure as well as at 20 lbs pressure gave a product m.p. 217–19°. On acetylation it gave an acetate m.p. 261–62°. Both the products showed no unsaturation when tested with tetranitromethane (cf. dihydro-taraxasterol m.p. 218–20° ; acetate m.p. 262–63°).

Finally the identity of the compound was established as taraxasterol by alongside T.L.C. with authentic samples of taraxasterol and its derivatives obtained from *Sonchus oleraceus* Linn. and I.R. Spectra.

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1. R. N. Chopra, S. L. Nayar and I. C. Chopra, Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants, Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, 1956, p. 230.

